

INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Kadirov Shahboz G'ayratjon o'gli

Lecturer of the Department of Exact and Natural Sciences

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Abstract. The comparative analysis of the identified indicators with the norms of the current physical education program for preparing schoolchildren for higher education in the field of physical culture and sports is the basis for the need to increase the volume of tools aimed at the general and special physical fitness of schoolchildren.

Key words: chest circumference, sports club, physical development, lung capacity, right and left palms dynamometric, sports base and sports equipment.

ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛ

Аннотация. Сравнительный анализ выявленных показателей с нормами действующей программы по физическому воспитанию подготовки школьников к высшему образованию в области физической культуры и спорта является основанием необходимости увеличения объема средств, направленных на общее и специальное физическая подготовленность школьников.

Ключевые слова: окружность груди, спортивный клуб, физическое развитие, объем легких, динамометрия правой и левой ладоней, спортивная база и спортивный инвентарь.

PF-5924 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 "On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "Wide implementation of a healthy lifestyle" dated October 30, 2020 solving the tasks specified in the Decree No. PF-6099 "On measures for the further development of mass sports" are considered urgent issues.

It was interesting to study the physical status of general secondary school students in order to determine their level of physical development and physical fitness.

Anthropometric characteristics of adolescents - body length and weight, chest circumference, lung capacity and dynamometric characteristics were determined according to the last years of schooling.

The results of the research are presented in Table 1. The length of the body is the main evaluative factor of physical development, which indicates the formation of the organism. Body length in tenth grade teenagers was 164.3 ± 3.8 cm, in eleventh grade the difference was 5 cm.

Indicators of physical development of teenagers studying in the final classes of secondary educational institutions in Fergana region

No	Indicators	10th grade			11th grade		
		X	s	V, %	X	s	V, %
1	Body length (cm)	164.3	3.8	2.3	169.3	3.9	2.3

2	Body weight (kg)	58	2.3	4	59	1.3	2
3	Chest circumference (cm)	78	8.4	10.8	80	4.1	4.7
4	Vital capacity of the lungs (ml)	3655	203	8	3770	186	5
5	Right palm power (kg)	37.8	3.9	10.3	38.2	4	10.7
6	Left palm strength (kg)	36.7	3.2	8.7	37.1	3.6	9.7
7	Waist strength (kg)	77	20.1	26.1	80	14.6	18.2

When assessing body weight indicators, it was found that they gradually increased over the years of study. In the tenth grade, the body weight of adolescents was equal to 58.0 ± 2.3 kg, in the eleventh grade there was a tendency to increase to 59 ± 1.3 kg.

It was found that in the 10th grade students compared to the 11th graders, when the reliability $r < 0.001$, the index of the chest circumference in the exhalation phase decreases and the vital capacity of the lungs increases. The evaluation showed that there were no significant differences in this test by years of study and it was within the limits of physiological norms.

The students' power capacity according to the dynamometric indicators of the right and left palms showed that no reliable changes were observed in the study data during the entire study period. Thus, in the tenth grade, the right palm strength of the students was 37 ± 3.9 kg, the left palm strength indicators were 36.7 ± 3.2 in insignificant variation distribution. There were no reliable changes in the studied indicators by the eleventh grade.

schoolchildren varies from 77 to 80 kg during the entire period of study, while the variation index decreased from 26.1 to 18.2 percent.

general secondary schools in Fergana region showed an unreliable increase in indicators ($r < 0.001$) for all studied parameters in the process of studying by stages. , which is the basis for the fact that there are shortcomings in the traditional system of physical education of students in the school system.

Of the identified indicators with the norms of the current physical education program for preparing schoolchildren for higher education in the field of physical culture and sports is the basis for the need to increase the volume of tools aimed at the general and special physical fitness of schoolchildren. Takes

A pedagogical experiment was conducted to determine the effectiveness of the methodology of preparing schoolchildren for higher education. Control and experimental groups were formed from 25 people whose difference was not reliable according to the investigated parameters.

The control group took part in the traditional physical education program, and the experimental group took part in the physical education methodology developed by us.

In order to prepare the students of the school invited by us for higher education in the field of physical education and sports, during the 10-11th grades, we organize 4 hours of optional training in physical education per week and every 6 months test standards for this subject. We checked the delivery in the experiment. In this process, doctor-pedagogical supervision was also established. 2 hours of training were organized on the basis of various exercises given by the mandatory teacher, and the remaining two hours were organized on the basis of training in the sports chosen by the students according to their interests.

The results of the conducted research showed that the indicators characterizing the physical fitness of schoolchildren increased significantly. A significant increase was found in the experimental group. The difference between the experimental group and the control group was 4.3% ($r < 0.05$) in speed and 3.8% ($r < 0.05$) in endurance.

We meant here that in recent years, due to the pandemic, only 100 m and 1000 m running tests have been taken to humanities higher educational institutions in the field of physical education and sports.

Implementation of the developed methodology for preparing schoolchildren for higher education in the field of physical education and sports showed that the indicators of physical fitness of students of the graduating class were significantly closer to the indicators of first-year students. Showed.

Experiments proved that 4 hours per week of optional physical culture and sports training for high school seniors had a good effect and increased the level of physical training of students for the profession in this field by 10.7%.

The purpose of the sports club in the general secondary school is to prepare and apply physical education and sports to educational and production activities, to organize a healthy lifestyle, ready for high production work in the defense of the Motherland and the chosen profession. is to influence the education of well-rounded specialists with abilities.

In a general secondary school, the sports club solves the following tasks:

- to involve the students, teachers, workers and their family members of the general secondary school in regular physical education and sports;
- to increase the social activity, professional readiness level of all members of the school team, reduce morbidity and strengthen their health, educate their physical and moral-volitional qualities;
- to work together with the rectorate of the higher educational institution, deans of faculties and public organizations on formation of knowledge, qualifications, skills and qualities, high self-sacrifice and decency in students in the necessary field;
- organization and holding of public health, physical culture and sports events;
- organization of amateur sports associations, clubs, sections and teams for sports;
- promotion of physical culture and sports, healthy lifestyle, meaningful organization of free time, involvement of athletes of the higher educational institution and those engaged in large-scale physical education in political and public events. The sports club carries out its work in direct

contact with classes and public organizations, as well as physical education teachers of the general secondary school and performs the following functions:

- teachers and workers of general secondary school introduce physical culture and sports to students' educational and work activities, life and recreation; promotes a healthy lifestyle, develops knowledge and skills of personal and public hygiene, self-control, first aid; fights to overcome bad habits;

- the established traditions of the general secondary school, the nature of training specialists, creates the necessary organizational and methodological conditions for team members to engage in various forms and types of physical culture and sports in accordance with their interests; introduces new forms and methods of physical education, advanced experiences and achievements of science; uses the material base rationally and efficiently;

- prepares sports club members to receive sports degrees;

- conducts work on physical rehabilitation with students with health defects, involves them in public - physical culture and sports events;

- organizes training courses on improving the qualifications of physical culture organizers, public sports referees, public guides and coaches, heads of sports section bureaus;

- provides support to general education schools, secondary schools in the organization of public health, physical culture and sports activities, supports the formation of amateur associations of children and teenagers based on their sports interests;

- organizes and conducts the training process in sports sections, groups, national teams, groups of sports interests;

- develops and implements a calendar plan of public health physical culture and sports events, ensures their safety;

- provides supervision of highly qualified student-athletes engaged in sports sections of the sports club, creates the necessary conditions for them to develop their sports skills;

- registers records and sports achievements, keeps accounts, forms national teams of the higher educational institution in sports and ensures their participation in competitions;

- organizes medical supervision of physical culture and sports participants in sections and groups of the sports club together with health authorities;

- ensures efficient and rational use of the material technical base; builds and organizes maintenance of common equipment, corners and health rooms with the help of club members; organizes the rental of sports facilities and sports equipment;

- organizes and conducts public sports contests and contests for the establishment of the best physical culture-health and sports activities among classes;

- encourages coaches, teachers and physical education activists who have achieved high results in the work process;

- prepares proposals for the development of physical education and sports for the complex plan of social development of general secondary school;

- organizes and conducts the collection of membership fees;

- carries out correspondence with appropriate organizations in accordance with the established procedure on the state and development of physical education and sports in the general secondary school;

- prepares current and perspective plans for the club's cost estimate, training and development of public physical culture and wellness.

The sports club is the first trade union organization in the general secondary school. It carries out all-round activities on the development of physical education and sports among students, teachers, workers and their family members on the basis of democracy, creative initiative and cross-functional conditions.

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